

Blockchain 3.0 and Decentralized Applications (From list, its Decentralized Applications)

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Current implementation of Bitcoin and Ethereum network is not ideal for Dapps as we are observing consistent congestion and higher transaction fees. DAPPS need much higher support of transactions, updates and operations than any of the popular established networks. Moreover, it needs to be able to handle better consensus mechanism to avoid the possibility of 51% attacks.

2. Aim

To find out the viable options for Blockchain 3.0 which is ideal for decentralized application.

3. REQUIREMENTS FOR DAPPS & BLOCKCHAIN 3.0

1. No Micro-transactions fees because DAPPS could be from social application to knowledge exchange blogs.
2. Proven Scalability.
3. Immune from DDOS attacks.
4. Proven script or language support.
5. Economic Model should be modeled in such a way that the speculations can be avoided. Dapps require stable financing for the longer terms and it can only be done through appropriate economic incentive structure.

4. PROBLEMS WITH CURRENT ESTABLISHED BLOCKCHAINS

BITCOIN

1. Congestion and higher fees on Bitcoin.
2. Secure but minimal support of the scripting.
3. Its not completely decentralized now as 60% of the transactions are handles through a few mining pools.

ETHEREUM

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1. Congested during ICOs.
2. Crypto kitties blocked the whole Ethereum network and made it unusable.
3. Transaction fees.

5. Research

At present EOS and Cardano seems solving most of the problems. Steemit has implemented the robust no fees micro-transaction, DPOS consensus(practically more decentralized than BTC or ETH) and stake based resource allocation. Moreover great economic structure of having three separate currencies solves the major issues of speculations and encouraged the long term commitments with the platform. The above blockchains will solve most of the problem for Dapps. A better consensus mechanism is yet to define for the practical fully decentralization. DPOS is the closest one which relies on a fixed number of the block producers.

6. Conclusions

Choosing the right platform for the Dapps is extremely critical as it may lead towards complete failure of the projects. Any blockchain which works based on the above principle should be termed as Blockchain 3.0 and must be chosen in order to ensure the project success.

7. Keywords

Dapps, Blockchain 3.0

Author biography

Sanjay Parihar Sanjay Parihar has completed Engineering degree from a renowned engineering collage (BIT) from India. He has overall 19 years of experience with architecting and building complex enterprise softwares from Financial, Federal and Other domains. His entrepreneurial venture has started with building MOOC in 2012. Later, he worked with arentRound.com which has been acquired recently.

His current venture, Kyndor inc, is working on building the Parents network over blockchain and encourage peer-peer communication with the fully data privacy. In addition, He is also a blockchain contributor for the CSA group.